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PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ADOLESCENTS IN PARENTAL CARE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the features of psychological counseling to parents on issues of irresponsibility and lack of independence of teenagers. During consultations between the teacher-psychologist and parents of teenagers, constructive methods of interaction, options for carrying out preventive and educational work with parents of teenagers are offered. With parents and teenagers recommendations on the contents of preventive and educational trainings are given.

Key words: advice, psychological help, prevention.

THE MAIN PART

In scientific and popular literature, the issues of providing psychological support to adolescents and their parents aimed at reducing the contradictions between the desire and desire of adolescents for independence and the psychological reluctance of parents to accept and support this news are discussed. is being done. behavior patterns of their children. Psychological support for parents often consists of helping parents to see the following feature: they are not adequately using the behavior models that they used in earlier periods of their children's lives. For example, in early childhood. We also want to contribute to the discussion on this topic. That is: perhaps not new, but based on the professional experience of the authors of the article, offering the option of organizing psychological support for child-parent relationships. This type of organization is aimed at forming new behavioral models and developing the psychological abilities of the participants of the interaction (adolescents and their parents). A pedagogical psychologist in the school system is a person who must find a balance between all participants of the educational process. expert. One of the important activities of a school psychologist is the psychological support of students. Adolescence is known as one of the most difficult periods in everyone's life. Hormonal changes, changes in leading activities, the search for self and the increased desire to separate from adults make the life of a teenager difficult and full of experiences. We often hear the phrase "they don't want to be responsible and mature". On the other hand, there are parents who turn to the school psychologist and complain about the irresponsibility and initiative of their teenage children.

The topic of separating teenagers from their families, developing their independence and psychological maturity is one of the most popular psychological tips for teenagers themselves and their parents. At the same time, each of the parties applying for psychological consultation has similar requests: teenagers do not understand how they can "prove to their parents that they are already adults", and parents explain that they "do not trust" the psychologist. nothing to the teenager because he is "not completely independent" ... "What responsibilities does the teenager currently have in the family/home?" to the question. Many parents raise their eyebrows in surprise and ask silently or loudly: "Why? He does nothing anyway!" they also do not have the experience of observing the performance of their duties by other family members. The formation of responsible behavior is a long and gradual process, requiring parents to show independence

depending on the abilities of the child according to the age characteristics of the child. It requires the creation of conditions, positive reinforcement in the form of positive evaluation and support in the process of learning independent forms of behavior. It will be more effective if it starts in childhood.

Psychological educational resources allow parents and legal representatives to expand their understanding of methods and methods that help to establish constructive interactions with children and adolescents and create situations that develop and strengthen the independent behavior model of adolescents. At the same time, it is important that the school psychologist remains in the position of an expert who is on the side of the child's interests, rather than delving into the personal or family problems of the parents. If the parents themselves need more in-depth psychotherapeutic help, the educational psychologist should properly refer the clients to certified specialists in the field of family or marital psychotherapy. Working with or only with the adolescent is less effective than joint counseling of the child and parent. The child is part of the family system, which always lives according to its rules and laws. If his behavior changes, the teenager returns to the family where there are specific patterns of behavior. And these schemes encourage the teenager to give up his purchases and "be the same". Child-parent counseling involves the establishment of communication in the parent-child pair, which gives the opportunity to talk, see the other's position and, most importantly, "hear" the emotions accumulated in each party. Such conversations help to identify the most problematic aspects of communication and to determine the "goals of counseling work". The experience of constructive communication can be used by the participants of consultations with parents in the future without the participation of a specialist. If there are difficulties in the relationship between parents and children at the elementary school age and there is no trust, adolescence becomes a "litmus test" for all previous problems.

Summary

Various methods and techniques can be used during psychological prevention. In our professional practice, parenting clubs, problem seminars and discussions aimed at increasing the psychological and pedagogical competence of parents in the field of interpersonal communication are especially popular. The format of the parents' club includes consideration of various topics related to teaching, upbringing, development of children, teaching methods of interaction with the child in conflict situations. Parenting effectiveness classes can be conducted together with children so that they can see the parents' communication style and use the skills they have learned. and each psychologist can choose the most suitable for a specific audience or situation, then the language and content of working with parents should be determined according to reliable scientific data.

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